

Prolong Fever in Elderly Man with Anemia, Lymphopenia, Thrombocytopenia, Ascites, Hypoalbuminemia, Hepatitis and Renal Failure Following Prostate Surgery: Emerging Invasive Fungal Infections By Candida Albicans, Sepedonium Species and Candida Tropicalis

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CASE SUMMARY

A 78-years-old male had fever for two weeks with appetite loss and weight loss. He had hypertension and chronic kidney disease. He underwent transurethral resection of prostate one month ago for benign prostatic hypertrophy. It was complicated by urinary tract infection due to *Klebsiella pneumoniae* two months prior to fever. Physical examination was unremarkable except mild anemia. Blood examination revealed anemia, lymphopenia, thrombocytopenia, transaminitis, high serum creatinine and high inflammatory markers (ESR, CRP and procalcitonin). Studies on imaging (chest radiograph, CT scan chest, abdomen and pelvis, ultrasound abdomen) were normal apart from gall stone and ascites. *Candida albicans* was detected in urine culture; parenteral voriconazole for two weeks followed by oral voriconazole for 3 weeks was given. However, fever persisted and bone marrow examination was proceeded. *Sepedonium* species was grown in fungal culture from bone marrow; and *Candida tropicalis* was identified in urine. He recovered with Amphotericin B therapy for 3 weeks followed by 8 weeks course of oral voriconazole. Awareness of emerging invasive fungal infections in patient with prolong fever is highlighted.

KEYWORD: prolong fever, *Candida albicans*, *Sepedonium* species, *Candida tropicalis*,

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INTRODUCTION

Prolong fever is a common in clinical practice. It is due to infection, autoimmune diseases, malignancy, endocrine

disease, drug induced and iatrogenic. Regarding infection, bacterial infection is the commonest. Infection due to fungus was rarely reported. A thorough history, physical

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examination, and standard laboratory testing are the corner stone of evaluation of the patient with prolong fever. A thorough history with emphasis on medical history, travel, exposure, prophylaxis, vaccination and immune status is important when considering likely infectious causes (McGregor & Moore, 2015). Hence, there are no standard approaches that are applicable for all patients with prolong fever (Bodey, 2000).

Bone marrow examination (histology and microbiology) is essential in final diagnosis hematological malignancy and infection in patient with prolong fever. Tubercle and giant cells can be seen in bone marrow histology in chronic granulomatous diseases like disseminated tuberculosis and invasive fungal infection. Ziehl- Nelson stain reveals acid fast bacilli (*Mycobacterium tuberculosis*); and special stain for fungus illustrates fungal spore. Fungal culture can identify specific species. This case report described three fungal infections in elderly; *Sepedonium* species was found in bone marrow; *Candida albicans* and *Candida tropicalis* were cultured in urine which were done one month apart. Awareness on emerging invasive fungal infections and anti-fungal resistance were discussed.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 78 year-old-man had low-grade fever for 10 days; it was associated with chills. His wife noticed irrational talk at the height of fever. He had hypertension for twenty years. For benign prostatic hypertrophy (BPH), he underwent transurethral resection of prostate (TURP) two months ago. The urine culture and sensitivity showed *Klebsiella* species; it was treated with levofloxacin and cefixime. He had raised serum creatinine (2.63 mg%) prior to surgery; and it was probably due to long standing hypertension.

Clinical examination was unremarkable apart from confusion and fever (100°F). There were no features of meningeal irritation or raised intracranial pressure. The patient did not have signs of chronic liver disease or organomegaly.

Initial blood tests revealed mild anemia (hemoglobin 11.8 g/dL, MCV 79 fL); reticulocyte count was raised 4.3% (0.5%-2.5%); total WBC count was normal ($5.9 \times 10^9/l$); absolute neutrophil count was low normal (ANC $4.2 \times 10^9/l$); absolute lymphocyte count was low (ALC $0.7 \times 10^9/l$); Monocyte count was normal ($0.6 \times 10^9/l$); Eosinophil count was $0.2 \times 10^9/l$; Basophils count was $0.02 \times 10^9/l$; and platelets count was $509 \times 10^9/l$. And, D Dimer was slightly high (1750 ngFEU/L) (normal <500 ng FEU/mL).

Other biochemistry tests showed raised blood urea 65.5 mg/dL; high serum creatinine 3.3 mg/dL; sodium 138 mmol/l; potassium 3.4 mmol/l; chloride 97 mmol/l; normal serum calcium 10.2mg/dl; uric acid 4.8mg/dl. Regarding liver profile, total bilirubin was slightly raised (1.2 mg/dL); normal ALT with raised AST (ALT 24.8 IU/L, AST 50.2 IU/L); raised serum alkaline phosphatase (576 IU/L) (normal 44-147

IU/L); normal total protein (71.2 g/L) with low albumin 25 g/L and high globulin 46.2 g/L.

Pus cell 5-10/ HPF was found in urine routine examination; RBCs was 30-40/ HPF; and albumin was positive (+1). It was probably due to indwelling urinary catheterization done during confusion and urinary tract infection. Urine ACR (Albumin Creatinine ratio) was slightly raised 0.3 mg/g (normal < 0.02mg/g). Urine for acid fast bacilli (AFB) was negative.

He was initially treated with meropenem; however, fever was swinging (104°F) and he was still drowsy. Fluid and electrolyte replacement was given.

For infection screening, serology test for HBV, HCV, HIV and VDRL testes were done and they were negative. Blood film examination for malaria parasite was negative. Culture and sensitivity tests for blood, urine and sputum were all negative; they were done twice over 3 weeks. Blood for CMV PCR was detected in very low titer (less than 200 IU/ml).

Ultrasound (abdomen and pelvic) showed mild enlargement of prostate (BPH grade I) and mild acute calculous cholecystitis. Chest X-ray (PA view) revealed normal. It is shown in photo (1). While awaiting further investigation results, general condition was deteriorating; falling weight and appetite. Fever was not responding to meropenem; thus, imipenem and levofloxacin were initiated. However, the fever was persistent with high-grade remitted in nature. Therefore, the second line investigations were continued.

The urine culture and sensitivity test was repeated; it was sterile. However, *Candida albicans* was detected in urine culture; parenteral voriconazole for two weeks followed by oral voriconazole for 3 weeks was given. However, fever persisted; the patient had dysuria. Serum tumor markers were unremarkable apart from mildly raised CA 19-9; it was 51.7 U/mL (normal < 39U/mL); AFP was normal, 1.17 IU/mL (<5.8); CEA was 3.78 ng/mL (normal <4.7 ng/mL); Cyfra was 1.06 ng/mL (normal <3.3 ng/mL); total PSA was 1.48 ng/mL (<1.5 ng/mL). For autoimmune disorder, ANA qualitative assay was done; ANA was positive for 1/80 dilution. Both blood for RA and Anti-CCP were negative. Blood for ENA profile was negative. CRP was very high; 46.5 mg/L (normal < 5mg/L). And ESR was high (46 mm/hr). Procalcitonin was high; 2.1ng/mL (normal < 0.5ng/mL). LDH was normal (70 IU/L) (normal 135-225 IU/L). Echocardiography revealed no evidence of vegetation or thrombus; LVEF was normal (60%).

Temperature kept on swinging; appetite was losing; body weight was falling; general condition was deteriorating. He became icteric with mild anemia. At that time, tip of the spleen became palpable; free fluid was detected too; bilateral pleural effusion became pronounced. The repeat full blood count (FBC) done after one week showed ongoing anemia, thrombocytopenia and lymphopenia. It was corrected with platelet transfusion and blood transfusion.

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Ascitic fluid study was done; it was transudative in nature; it contained few WBCs and RBCs; ADA (Adenosine deaminase) was 21.1 U/L (normal < 33 U/L); it was sterile on culture. QuantiFERON-TB Gold Plus (QFT) ELISA was negative. Ascitic fluid cytology was negative. Ascitic fluid culture for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* was negative; the culture took 3 months. As ascites was relatively refractory to diuretics and stool for fecal occult blood by FIT (fecal immunochemical test) was detected, oesophago-gastro-duodenoscopy with colonoscopy were done to rule out malignancy of stomach and large intestine. It revealed multiple colonic polyps.

NECT scan (chest and abdomen) showed minimal bilateral pleural effusions, cardiomegaly, gall stone without features of cholecystitis and moderate ascites. They are illustrated in photo (2-10).

Despite antibiotics and supportive management, the patient condition was not improving. The investigation results did not pin point the exact cause of high-grade fever in this patient. Blood serology for various fungal antibody tests (*Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Blastomyces dermatitidis*, *Coccidioides immitis*, *Histoplasma capsulatum*) was negative. Therefore, tarzobactam was prescribed; the peak of temperature became lower.

Therefore, bone marrow examination was done to exclude bone marrow pathology and lymphoproliferative disorder. Bone marrow aspirate flowcytometry for chronic lymphoproliferative disorder showed no definite evidence of chronic lymphoproliferative disorder. Bone marrow aspiration revealed hemodiluted with few segmented neutrophils and lymphocytes only; fungal elements were seen.

Bone marrow trephine was compatible with hypoplastic myelodysplastic marrow. Bone marrow iron store was adequate. Fungal elements in bone marrow trephine biopsy were positive in GMS (Grocott's methenamine silver) stain. It is shown in photo 10 & 11. Therefore, the patient was treated with intravenous Amphotericin B (conventional) (initially 0.25 mg/kg daily and gradually increased to 1 mg/kg daily); and it was continued for 3 weeks. Then, the treatment was consolidated by oral voriconazole for 8 weeks.

Bone marrow trephine biopsy was consistent with chronic granulomatous inflammation as it contained ill-formed granulomas, Langerhans type giant cells and macrophages. Acid fast bacilli was not seen in bone marrow trephine Z-N stain. Fungal elements were seen in bone marrow aspirate for fungal culture; and the culture revealed *Sepedonium* species. Moreover, the urine for fungal study also revealed *Candida tropicalis*; it was sensitive to fluconazole, voriconazole, caspofungin, micafungin and amphotericin B; and, it was resistant to flucytosine.

General condition of the patient improved gradually following antifungal therapy. Fever did not rise after initiation of Amphotericin B therapy. He became fully consciousness and alert. However, thrombocytopenia persisted. And, the patient passed melaena stool; platelet count was $17 \times 10^9/L$ at that time. Therefore, he was given platelet transfusion and four units of blood transfusion.

Four weeks after initiation of amphotericin therapy, platelet count, absolute lymphocyte count and serum albumin rose slowly; serum creatinine reduced to his previous level. After completion of antifungal therapy, the patient had good appetite. Body weight increased gradually.

DISCUSSION

Prolong fever is common in daily clinical practice. The differential diagnosis of prolong fever are infections, malignancies, autoimmune conditions and miscellaneous. A thorough history and physical examination were important initially as well as daily ward round. New physical findings would be the clue to cause of prolong fever or the sequel of treatment (McGregor & Moore, 2015). And further investigation was individualized; there was no standard approaches that were applicable for all patients (Bodey, 2000). Newer diagnostic modalities, including updated serology, viral cultures, computed tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging, had important role in assessing patients with prolong fever (Roth & Basello, 2003).

A variety of bacterial infections as well as viral, parasitic and fungal infections cause prolong fever. Infective causes were the most common in immunocompetent host as well as immunodeficient host. Prolong fever in immunocompetent host due to invasive fungal infection (IFI) was very rare. This patient had invasive fungal infection; it was confirmed by bone marrow fungal culture. He was not diabetic. Therefore, the clinicians should have awareness on increasing incidence of IFI even in low-risk patients. It was also suggested by Guo et al (T.-M. Guo et al., 2019). This is one reason for case reporting.

There are several reasons for increase in prevalence of IFI worldwide: increasing elderly population due to longer life expectancy; the rising number of immunocompromised patients as a result of immunosuppressive treatments for transplantation, autoimmune diseases, and immunodeficiency diseases; the growing number of cases with diabetes mellitus; and misuse of medication like corticosteroids and broad-spectrum antibiotics. Studies on IFI reported that its prevalence was high in immunodeficient hosts such as bone marrow transplant recipient; neutropaenic host; those with intravascular or other catheters (parenteral nutrition), prostheses, anatomical barrier loss (e.g., burns); those receiving immunosuppressant therapy; and, those with prior antimicrobial therapy. This patient did not have diabetes mellitus; however, the attributing factor would be his age

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(nearly 80 years), having indwelling urinary catheter, and prior broad-spectrum antibiotics for urinary tract infection. The study from Turkiye pointed out the importance of nosocomial infections (Ozer et al., 2015) (Esen & Leblebicioglu, 2004). The presence of *Candida* species in the urinary tract system (Candiduria) was found in 10-15% of the cases with urinary tract infection (UTI). The predisposing factors for candiduria were reported as antibacterial agents, urinary tract instrumentation, diabetes mellitus, invasive therapies, and prolonged hospital stay. Among *Candida* species, *Candida albicans* was the most common isolated species from candiduric patients. Owing to increasing resistance to antifungal drugs, non-*albicans* *Candida* species such as *Candida glabrata*, *Candida krusei*, *Candida parapsilosis* and *Candida tropicalis* was emerging (Gharaghani et al., 2018). First urine culture of this patient revealed *Candida albicans*. And, 5 weeks course of voriconazole was given initially. However, both fever and dysuria did not make improvement. Having indwelling catheter was a risk factor for candiduria in this patient according to Mohammadnejad et al (Mohammadnejad et al., 2024).

And, urine culture for fungus repeated at one month showed the growth of *Candida tropicalis*. Therefore, it may indirectly reflect increasing resistance to antifungal drugs in Myanmar. It supported the problem of anti-fungal resistance found in several studies (Barnes et al., 2024) (Stohs & Zimmer, 2020). Wingard et al suggested the importance of antifungal susceptibility testing (Shetty et al., 2024) and antifungal stewardship for IFI (Wingard, 2004) (Lafaurie et al., 2010). Moreover, Mori et al encouraged to monitor therapeutic efficacy of anti-fungal drug (Segal et al., 2007) (Mori et al., 2024).

Having *Candida tropicalis* in urine of this patient may indicate emerging non-*albicans* *Candida* as a possible cause of candiduria in Myanmar. It was mentioned that *Candida tropicalis* was notorious for antifungal resistance to the azoles, polyenes, and echinocandins. Moreover, *Candida tropicalis* was an osmotolerant microorganism; and *Candida tropicalis* had the ability to survive to high salt concentration (Zuza-Alves et al., 2017). *Candida tropicalis* was commonly related with candidemia; and mortality rates was high as above 40% (Lima et al., n.d.) (Arellano-Galindo, Eugenio, Elva, Jesús, María de Los Ángeles, et al., 2017).

In this patient, diagnosis IFI was confirmed by bone marrow culture and histology. The diagnosis and treatment of IFI was still challenging due to its complexity and non-specificity (Wingard, 2004). Early diagnosis was essential as IFI had high morbidity, physical dysfunction and mortality (Seyedjavadi et al., n.d.) (Barnes et al., 2024) (Stohs & Zimmer, 2020). Therefore, the strategy of initiating either 'empirical' or 'preemptive' antifungal therapy before the final diagnosis in vulnerable patients was suggested in early

20 century (Zimmermann-Hösli et al., 1988) (Ruhnke et al., 2012) (Lionakis et al., 2023) (Hassan et al., 2014) (Livio Pagano et al., 2011) (Beed et al., 2014). Lai et al found that delayed antifungal therapy in patients with IFI resulted in prolonged hospital stay and death (Lai et al., 2005); late diagnosis was an independent adverse prognostic factor. In this patient total hospital stay was 60 days. However, the patient recovered completely after completion of second time anti-fungal therapy. He had bone marrow recovery; return of liver function to normal; and improvement in renal function. The incidence of fungal disease is increasing worldwide. New fungal diseases are emerging. Managing fungal diseases is challenging; only four classes of antifungal drugs are available, resistance to these drugs is increasing (Sobel et al., 2000), and no vaccines have been approved (Oliveira et al., 2023). Invasive fungal infections (IFI) due to *Sepedonium* species was very rare. This patient had *Sepedonium* species; it was cultured in bone marrow. There were giant cells in bone marrow histology as another evidence. *Sepedonium* sp. is a saprophytic fungus that inhabits soil and plant material. A case of *Sepedonium* sp. infection following graft failure accompanied by previous cytomegalovirus infection in a patient with hematopoietic stem cell transplantation was reported in 2017 (Arellano-Galindo, Eugenio, Elva, Jesús, Ángeles, et al., 2017). According to survey done in America, four *Sepedonium* species could be identified and characterized, viz.: *S. ampullosporum*, *S. chrysospermum*, *S. laevigatum* and the newly described species *S. loyorum* (Binimelis-Salazar et al., 2021). In this patient, we could not have laboratory facility to differentiate sub-species. Fungal diseases were found to be an important determinant of survival in immunocompromised patients and in patients with chronic illness (Oren & Paul, 2014). Therefore, this patient reminded the clinician on awareness of fungal diseases.

Invasive fungal infection (IFI) in this patient suppressed bone marrow function; anemia, lymphopenia and thrombocytopenia. Anemia in this patient was due to both bone marrow suppression by IFI and reduced erythropoietin production by kidney (chronic kidney disease). Having thrombocytopenia in this patient was due to several reasons: IFI causing bone marrow dysfunction; DIC as a result of septicemia (fungemia). Platelet count in this patient increased gradually following antifungal therapy; it supported the possibility of suppression of megakaryocytic series in bone marrow by fungus. Some report pointed out platelet dysfunction in fungal infection (Speth et al., 2014). And there was correlation between thrombocytopenia and fungal infection/sepsis (Kavthekar et al., 2019) (Bhat Y. et al., n.d.) (Perkhofer et al., 2009). Low platelet count in IFI lead to chronic form- chronic thrombocytopenia in some study (Ayesh (Haj Yousef) & Alawneh, 2011).

Adherence of lymphocytes to the fungus was found to be the first step in the direct lymphocyte-mediated antifungal effect

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against *Candida albicans* (Forsyth & Mathews, 2002); it might probably led to low absolute lymphocyte count. Ortega-Loubon et al reported that “Low lymphocyte count ($<0.7 \times 10^9/L$) was an independent predictor of mortality in patients with candidemia and might serve as a biomarker for predicting candidemia-associated mortality and poor outcome” (Ortega-Loubon et al., 2019). In this patient, absolute lymphocyte count was low initially; it was at low level for almost 50 days. According to Yang et al, broad-spectrum antibacterial therapy prior to CAR-T therapy infusion and prolonged lymphocyte deficiency were found to be risk factors for development of IFI in patients with hematological malignancy (Yang et al., 2022). This patient

CONCLUSION

Prolong fever is common in daily practice. Invasive fungal infections (IFI) are increasing even in low-risk patients. Among the *Candida* species, both *Candida albicans* and non-*albicans Candida* species cause candiduria. Early diagnosis and timely anti-fungal therapy can save the life of the patient. Bone marrow trephine biopsy and culture for fungus is essential in diagnosis of IFI. IFI due to *Sepedonium* species caused anemia, lymphopenia, thrombocytopenia, liver impairments, renal dysfunction, hypoalbuminemia and ascites. Awareness of IFI is important in patient with prolong fever particularly it is associated with lymphopenia and thrombocytopenia.

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had several broad spectrum anti-bacterial therapy and prolonged lymphocyte deficiency; therefore, he was prone to IFI. Low lymphocyte count together with CD4 lymphocyte count and the levels of (1, 3)- β -d-glucan (BDG) and galactomannan (GAL) were found to be strongly associated with IFIs (Zhang et al., 2025)(Herdiman, 2005). Previously, low absolute lymphocyte count was related with viral infection, tuberculosis, connective tissue disorder and lymphoma (Z. Guo et al., 2021). In patient with prolong fever and lymphopenia, IFI should be one of the differential diagnoses.

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Figure 1. Course of the illness by days

Table 1. Serial changes in hematology and biochemical profile

Parameter	Day '0_'	Day '0'	Day '7'	Day '14'	Day '21'	Day '28'	Day '35'	Day '42'	Day '49'	Day '56'	Day '63'
Hb (gm%)	9.1	11.4	10	11.2	10.7	8.5	9.4	10	9.6	11	11.1
TWBC	3.9	4.7	4.5	4.8	5.3	2.9	2.5	2.4	3.4	5.0	4.0
ANC	1.9	3.7	4.0	4.4	4.8	1.8	1.3	1.1	1.9	2.6	2.3
ALC	1.6	0.6	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.2	1.5	1.3
AMC	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.4
Platelets	103	50	32	45	79	32	150	181	123	148	159
D dimer		1750			1298	275					
CRP			46.7								1.5
ESR											
Procalcitonin		2.1									
APTT						32.3					
Bilirubin		1.19	4.4				1.02		0.8	0.2	0.5
SGOT (AST)		50.2	50			28.5	30.4	36.1	46.4	49.5	45.2
SGPT (ALT)		24.8	14.6			6.0	10.5	10.2	33.8	23.2	35.2
Alkaline Phosphatase		576	628				311	206	235	217	186
Total Protein		71	63.7	57.6							
Albumin		25	25.8	22.5	23.1		25.7	26.9	38.5	37.1	
Globulin		46	38	35.1							
rGT		229									
urea				110	136	92	77.1	33	66.7	95	
creatinine	1.3	3.37	3.27	3.3	4.24	2.75	3.15	1.74	2.16	2.9	2.5
sodium	140	138	145	124	142	138	145	137	141	138	139
potassium	2.9	4.5	4.1	2.9	3.6	3.3	4.5	4.5	4.5	5.1	3.9
Ca		10.9	10.7								
LDH		398			202						
phosphate			0.95								

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Photo (1) Normal chest taken from CT (October 2024) except old healed fracture right clavicle

Photo (2) HRCT chest (December 2024) showing bilateral mild pleural effusion, amount increased compared October 2024

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Photo (3) HRCT chest (October 2024) showing normal lung except bilateral minimal pleural effusion

Photo (4) HRCT chest (December 2024) showing normal lung except bilateral mild pleural effusion; amount increased compared to October 2024

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Photo (5) HRCT chest (December 2024) showing small pulmonary nodule in right upper zone subpleural area

Photo (6) HRCT abdomen (October 2024) showing gall stone

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Photo (7) HRCT abdomen (December 2024) showing gall stone; no changes compared to October 2024

Photo (8) HRCT abdomen (taken in December 2024) showing no evidence of lymphadenopathy

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Photo (9) MRCP cholangiogram (taken in November 2024) showing gall stone with normal biliary tree

Photo (10) MRI Abdomen (taken in November 2024) showing normal except small left renal cyst

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Photo (11) Histology of Bone Marrow Trepine Biopsy showing granuloma (green arrow) and Langhan’s giant cell (red arrow)

Photo (12) Histology of Bone Marrow Trepine Biopsy (High power view) with GMS (Grocott's methenamine silver) stain showing numerous fungal spores indicated by blue arrows

Photo (13.a) Temperature chart on admission showing intermittent fever

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Photo (13.b) Temperature chart in November showing almost normal temperature

Photo (13.c) Temperature chart in early December revealing recurrence of fever

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